

Analysis of the Performance of the Shallot Market in East Lombok Regency

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Abstract: This research departs from the importance of Shallot agricultural products as a horticultural commodity with high economic value in Indonesia, in the West Nusa Tenggara area, especially in East Lombok Regency. However, shallot farmers in this area face various challenges in marketing, such as limited access, dependence on middlemen, and low bargaining position of farmers. This prompted the author to analyze the performance of the shallot market in East Lombok Regency in order to provide efficient recommendations to improve farmers' welfare.

The main problem studied is how the shallot marketing channel is structured, marketing behavior occurs, and the level of marketing efficiency in various shallot marketing distribution channels in East Lombok Regency. To answer this problem, the research used a descriptive-quantitative analysis approach by collecting primary data through direct interviews with farmers and traders, as well as analyzing secondary data from related sources to quantitative research data.

The research methodology used in this research is a descriptive method. The descriptive method is a research method that attempts to describe a symptom, event, incident occurring now.

The results of this research area. Farmers - Collectors - Wholesalers - Retailers with a volume of 33,540 kg, b. Farmers – Collectors – Retailers with a volume of 44,400 kg, c. Farmers – Wholesalers – Retailers with a volume of 45,700 kg and d. Farmers – Retailers with a volume of 16,380 kg. While the marketing function of shallots can be carried out by farmers, collectors, wholesalers and retailers, farmers carry out the marketing function of sales, marketing costs and risk bearing costs, market information. Collectors carry out marketing, purchasing, sales, transportation, storage, standardization/sorting, marketing costs, risk bearing and market information functions. Wholesalers carry out the functions of marketing, purchasing, selling, transportation, storage, standardization/sorting, marketing costs, risk bearing, and market information. Retailers perform marketing, purchasing, selling, risk bearing and market information functions. Meanwhile, the most efficient channel is the IV channel (from farmers directly to retailers).

Keywords: market performance, shallots, marketing channels, marketing functions and efficiency.

I. INTRODUCTION

According to data from the Central Statistics Agency, Indonesia's shallot production will reach 19,823,602 tonnes in 2022. The highest shallot production center is in the Central Java region with production of 5,924,887 tonnes of shallots. The area with the most production in Central Java is Brebes Regency producing 3,835,111 tons. Then followed by East Java Regency with production reaching 478,393 tons of shallots. Nganjuk Regency is the district with the most shallot production in East Java. The number three province producing shallots is West Sumatra reaching 207,376 tonnes of shallots.

West Nusa Tenggara Province is the fourth province producing the most shallots in Indonesia, namely 1,857,954 tons after the provinces of Central Java, East Java and West Sumatra. Bima Regency is the largest producer in NTB Province producing 1,362,924 tons of shallots in 2022. Then followed by Sumbawa Regency, East Lombok Regency, Dompu

Regency and North Lombok Regency. The following is the distribution of shallot producing areas in West Nusa Tenggara Province by Regency/City in 2021/2022 according to data sources from the NTB Provincial Central Statistics Agency.

Aikmel District is one of the sub-districts in East Lombok Regency consisting of 24 villages. The community's largest income comes from the agricultural sector. One of the crop commodities cultivated is shallot plants. According to Puspitasari (2017) the types of shallot varieties planted are the Ganjuk, Bauci and Lenda varieties. Shallot planting is carried out 5 times a year. The main harvest occurs from January to February with a harvest area of around 2,525 ha with a production output of 25,512 tons of shallots.

Field data shows that the tendency of activities in the marketing performance of shallots is that the harvest obtained by farmers in Aikmel District, East Lombok Regency is sold to middlemen or investors. Shallot farmers carry out marketing involving middlemen and wholesalers in their marketing system. Farmers only sell to marketing institutions, namely middlemen and wholesalers. Access to markets (*marketing of harvested shallots*) is the main problem faced by shallot farmers in Aikmel District, East Lombok Regency. This means that farmers have problems with their bargaining position and low power over middlemen or shallot marketing channel agencies in Aikmel District, East Lombok Regency.

To analyze marketing performance, standard prices are needed from each month's period per unit kilogram of each retail price of shallots in East Lombok Regency. In the following table.

The price of red onion commodities has often fluctuated. The market price for red onions in East Lombok Regency will be highest in May 2023 at Rp. 41,444/kg while the lowest price for shallots will be in September 2023 at Rp. 22,055/kg. Aikmel District, there is a pattern of shallot marketing performance which shows that demand will increase if the quantity demanded is higher than production. Conversely, the price of shallots will decrease while production increases, An'im Fattach (2017)

The length and shortness of the marketing channel formed from the interaction of marketing institutions will influence prices accepted by consumers and the price accepted by farmers as producers. However, it has not yet been determined Which part of the market institutions sest the price of shallots. Apart from that, it is not yet known how the performance of marketing channels , marketing functions and market performance are formed in the shallot marketing process in Aikmel sub-district , East Lombok Regency, so the author feels interested in studying it in depth. Based on the background above, it is very necessary to carry out research with the title: "*Shallot Market Performance Analysis in East Lombok Regency*".

This research aims: (1) Analyzing shallot marketing channels in East Lombok Regency (2) Analyzing shallot marketing functions in East Lombok Regency (3) Analyzing shallot marketing efficiency in East Lombok Regency.

II. METHODOLOGY

The method used in this research is descriptive and quantitative methods of operational efficiency. The descriptive method is a research method that attempts to describe a symptom, event, incident happening right now. Descriptive research focuses attention on actual problems as they exist when the research takes place (Noor, 2016). Meanwhile, measurement and analysis of operational efficiency uses descriptive-quantitative methods. Study implemented from February 2024 to April 2024.

Determination of Sample Locations: The research location chosen was Aikmel District using purposive sampling (intentionally) based on the consideration that this area is one of the shallot production centers in East Lombok Regency which has the largest shallot production. Then four villages were determined as sample research locations, namely Keroya Village, Kembang Kerang Village, Kalijaga Village and East Kalijaga Village.

Determination of Respondents: Determining the total number of samples or farmer respondents was quota *sampling*, namely 60 shallot farmers. Meanwhile, the distribution in each sample village was *proportional sampling*, namely 15 people in Kembang Kerang Village, 24 people in Keroya Village, 17 people in Kalijaga Village and 4 people in East Kalijaga. The sample collection or selection technique was carried out by *accidental sampling*. Meanwhile, determining the sampling technique for marketing institutions uses *snowball sampling* or tracing.

Flower village $166/626 \times 60 = 15$

Keroya village $258/626 \times 60 = 24$

Kalijaga Village $180/626 \times 60 = 17$

East Kalijaga $16/626 \times 60 = 4$

Table 1. The number of respondents to research on the analysis of shallot market performance in East Lombok Regency is as follows:

No	Respondent	Amount
1	Shallot Farmers	60
2	Collector	7
3	Wholesalers	6
4	Retailer	23
Amount		98

Source: UPTPP, Aikmel District, East Lombok Regency

Data Type: The data collection method was carried out using the *survey method*. Data was collected in the form of primary data and secondary data. Primary data collection was carried out using the interview method using a list of questions (questionnaire) to shallot farmers in Aikmel District, East Lombok Regency. Secondary data is data obtained from the results of literature studies and official publications from various agencies. This data comes from official government data, research journals, literature and literature related to this research as well as publications from the National Central Statistics Agency, BPS West Nusa Tenggara Province and BPS East Lombok Regency.

Data Source: Primary data, researcher collect them directly. Technique used by researchers to obtain primary data, namely by distributing questionnaires to farmers and shallot traders in Aikmel District. Meanwhile secondary data obtained from various sources such as the Department of Industry and Trade website, Central Statistics Agency data, books, reports, journals and the internet. How to Collect Data. Data collection was carried out using *survey techniques*, namely data collection by compiling a list of questions asked to respondents from a number of population units at the same time (Noor, 2016). Meanwhile, secondary data collection uses document study techniques sourced from several studies, especially from research reports from research journals.

Data Analysis: The analysis used refers to the research objectives, namely: 1) to produce data analysis in the form of shallot marketing channels in East Lombok Regency; 2) to produce data analysis in the form of shallot marketing functions in East Lombok Regency; and 3) to produce data analysis in the form of shallot marketing efficiency in East Lombok Regency.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Results and Discussion :

The research results and discussion in this research will be discussed in detail according to the variables in the research as follows:

Characteristics of Respondent Farmers

Respondents in this research were farmers and traders. The indicators used to describe farmer respondents are age, education, farming experience, land area and partnership status.

(1) Age of Respondent Farmers

According to Hurlock (1994), based on adult age groups, respondents can be grouped into three, namely early adulthood (aged 18-40 years), middle adulthood (aged 40-60 years) and late adulthood (aged over 60 years). The data obtained is as follows:

Table 2. Number of Respondents Based on Age in Aikmel District 2023.

No	Respondent Age (Years)	Number of people)	Percentage (%)
1	33 - 64 (Productive)	29	48
2	> 64 (No Productive)	12	20
Amount		60	100

Source: Processed Primary Data (2023)

According to Kominfo (2022), the population criteria for the labor force is divided into two, namely the productive age population and the unproductive population. The productive age population is the population aged 15–64 years. Meanwhile,

the unproductive population is the population aged <15 years and >65 years. According to Suparmoko (2002), labor is the population of working age or the total population in a country producing goods or services. Labor working age is between 15-64 years. The three activities of this group are looking for work, going to school, and taking care of the household . Even though they are not working, they are considered to be physically or at any time able to join in the work, as children who are still studying and do not have work skills.

The age range for workers is between 20-40 years. This age is considered very effective for the workforce because if the age is under 20 years, generally the individual still does not have mature enough skills and is still in the educational process. Meanwhile, when the age exceeds 40 years, an individual's physical abilities decrease (Yasin, 2016). Manpower refers to the population aged between 15-64 years or the total population in a country capable of producing goods and services if there is demand for their labor and are willing to participate in these activities (Arisandi, 2018) .

(2) Respondent Farmer Education

The education level of shallot farmers in Aikmel District varies greatly . However, table 2. shows that there are many Domination by farmers is only at the elementary and high school and middle school education levels. Meanwhile, there is only one farmer with a bachelor's degree level of education. This is due to having an educational level higher will switch professional levels as a teacher or entrepreneur because they already have experience in marketing techniques and experience.

Table 3. Education Level of Shallot Farmers in Aikmel District 2023.

No	Education	Amount	Percentage (%)
1	Elementary School/Equivalent	29	48
2	S M P/Equivalent	12	20
3	S M A/Equivalent	18	30
4	College	1	2
	Amount	60	100

Source: Processed Primary Data (2023)

(3) Land Ownership Area

The results of data analysis based on the table above show that the area of land cultivated by shallot farmers in Aikmel District is relatively narrow. As many as 78% of shallot farmers have rice fields of less than 0.5 Ha. This shows that shallot farming in Aikmel District is generally carried out on a small scale and farmers in the small category are 47 people or 78%, 13 shallot farmers with a percentage of 22% are included in the medium category. This cultivated land area is included in the narrow land category because the cultivated land area is less than 0.5. This description is strengthened by the theory of Sajogyo, (1977) in Mahmud (2019) who categorizes farmers into three groups, namely small farmers with a farming area of <0.5 ha, medium farmers with a farming area of 0.5-1 ha, 0 ha, and large farmers with farming land area >1.0 ha.

Table 4. Red Onion Farmers' land area in Aikmel District 2023.

No	Land area (Ha)	Amount	Percentage (%)
1	< 0.5	47	78
2	0.5-1	13	22
3	> 1	0	0
	Amount	60	100

Source: Processed Primary Data (2023)

(4) Experience in Shallot Farming

Based on the results of interviews with respondents in In the Aikmel District area, the average onion farming experience is more than 10 years or more. Seen from the table above, 7 respondents with 12% have 11-20 years of experience in cultivating land, especially growing shallots, 53 respondents with 88% have experience in cultivating shallots for more than

21 years. This means that the average shallot farmer has had extraordinary experience in growing shallots for more than 10 years. So it can be seen in the table that there are no respondents under 10 years who are still cultivating shallots with a percentage of 0%. This shows that the experience and abilities of farmers with shallot planting patterns are above average.

Table 5. Experience of Shallot Farming in Aikmel District 2023.

No	Experience Try farmer (year)	Amount (person)	Percentage (%)
1	5 – 10	0	0
2	11 – 20	7	12
3	> 21	53	88
Amount		60	100

Source: Processed Primary Data (2023)

In the case of red onion sales in Aikmel District, 60 respondents or farmers carried out the buying and selling process directly by the farmers themselves, without using officially established work partners. This means that farmers are free to sell their shallot harvest to all collectors or dealers around where they live. The consequences faced by shallot farmers with this independent system in distributing/marketing their harvests individually, when the harvest is abundant, they must be ready to sell shallots at low prices. This means that farmers often suffer losses in terms of both costs and capital during cultivation.

Trader Characteristics: Respondents in this study were traders. The indicators used to explain farmer respondents are age, education and trading experience. There are 36 traders involved in the marketing channels in the shallot research process in Aikmel District. Consisting of 7 collectors, 6 wholesalers and 23 retailers. Most of the collecting traders come from Aikmel District, obtaining their supply of shallots from farmers directly with a price agreement between both parties. Where there is bargaining for non-partnered farmers and no bargaining for partner farmers.

Market collectors on Lombok Island are divided into three, namely district collectors at the Aikmel market, Aikmel District, district collectors at the Paok Motong market, Masbagik District, East Lombok Regency, and collectors at the Mandalika Regional Market, Mataram City. Meanwhile, 12 people are involved in the distribution of shallots, consisting of small market retailers and home traders. The characteristics of trader respondents considered in this research are age, gender, level of education and trading experience.

Table 6. Characteristics of Wholesaler Respondents Based on Age in Aikmel District 2023.

No	Age of Retailer Respondents (Years)	Amount (Person)	Percentage (%)
1	32 -64 (Productive)	25	100
2	> 64 (Not Productive)	0	0
Amount		25	100
Average Age of Retailers		43 years old	

Source: Processed Primary Data (2023)

The table shows that the age of shallot traders ranges from 33-64 years, meaning that shallot traders in Aikmel District are 100% productive. According to Kominfo, (2020), the productive age population is the population aged 15–64 years. Meanwhile, the unproductive population is the population aged <15 years and >65 years.

Table 7. Characteristics of Collecting Trader Respondents Based on Age in Aikmel District 2023 .

No	Age of Collector Respondents (Years)	Number of people)	Percentage (%)
1	33-64 Productive	7	100
2	> 64 Unproductive	0	0
Amount		7	100
Average Age of Collecting Traders		47	

Source: Processed Primary Data (2023)

The table above shows that the age of shallot traders ranges from 33-64 years, meaning that shallot traders in Aikmel District are 100% productive. According to Kominfo (2020), the productive age population is the population aged 15–64 years. Meanwhile, the unproductive population is the population aged <15 years and >65 years.

Table 8. Characteristics of Wholesaler Respondents Based on Age in Aikmel District 2023.

No	Major Respondents (Years)	Number of people)	Percentage (%)
1	33-64 Productive	5	100
2	> 64 Unproductive	0	0
Amount		5	100
The average age of wholesalers is 50.5 years			

Source: *Processed Primary Data (2023)*

The table above shows that the productive age of shallot sellers, traders and collectors in Aikmel District ranges from 15-64 years. This productive age is seen from the length of work and the individual's ability to analyze a transaction process taking place in the market. This ability to analyze is an indicator that determines a person's productive age in carrying out daily activities according to the individual's levels and abilities. This is in line with information from Kominfo (2020), that the productive age population is the population aged 15–64 years. Meanwhile, the unproductive population is the population aged <15 years and >65 years.

The red onion distribution process in Aikmel District involves 10 traders consisting of traditional traders, retailers and collectors. The number of traders can be seen from the sample locations where the research took respondents. These 10 people consist of five women who function as retail traders around villages or hamlets, three men as dealers or traders, and two collectors or big bosses in the Aikmel District area. Collectors are meant here to be places where farmers sell their shallot harvest using a wholesale system and become customers for farmers to sell the price of their harvest. These data results do not include home collectors as a whole in Aikmel District.

Table 9. Education Status Level of Shallot Retailers in Aikmel District 2023.

No	Retailer Education	Amount	Percentage (%)
1	Elementary School/Equivalent	6	26
2	S M P/Equivalent	9	39
3	S M A/Equivalent	8	35
Amount		23	100

Source: *Processed Primary Data (2023)*

Table 10. Education Status Level of Shallot Collectors in Aikmel District 2023.

No	Collector Education	Amount	Percentage (%)
1	Elementary School/Equivalent	1	14
2	Middle School/Equivalent	3	43
3	High School/Equivalent	3	43
Amount		7	100

Source: *Processed Primary Data (2023)*

Table 11. Education Status Level of Shallot Wholesalers in Aikmel District 2023

No	Big Education	Amount	Percentage (%)
1	Elementary School/Equivalent	1	17
2	Middle School/Equivalent	3	50
3	High School/Equivalent	2	33
Amount		6	100

Source: *Processed Primary Data (2023)*

Based on the table above showing the education level of retailers, traders in Aikmel are dominated by high school graduates. Then middle school and finally elementary school. Even higher education alumni have not yet joined the shallot marketing system in Aikmel District. The buying and selling abilities of these traders and collectors were acquired autodidactically based on experience during transactions in the market.

They gained this experience after working for a long time at one of the large UD/CVs in the Aikmel District area. Then, little by little, they tried to buy directly from shallot farmers and distribute them using a deposit system. This entrustment system is distributed via goods trucks to traders for marketing outside the island of Lombok. Trust capital and the existence of previous social interactions in the market become the basis for transactions and distribution. This means that these big collectors took a long time to become big and known to traders outside the island of Lombok. It took 15-20 years to process. The researcher got this explanation directly from the story of large collectors in Aikmel District through an unstructured interview process. Then validated with questionnaires and structured interviews with other respondents.

Marketing Channel Analysis: Market research is the process of collecting and analyzing information about customers, competitors and market trends . Carried out to understand the needs, preferences and demands in a particular market. The goal of market research is to gain insight in-depth and valuable can be used for developing marketing strategies, making business decisions, and identifying new market opportunities. Keep in mind that market research needs to be updated regularly because customer needs and preferences can change over time.

In the shallot marketing process in Aikmel District, there are four types of marketing channels formed involving two marketing institutions. The existence of this marketing channel influences the level of distribution costs and prices paid by consumers. The four marketing channels can be explained in Figure 5 below:

Image description of the Shallot Marketing Chain in Aikmel District in 2023, as follows. Channel I of the marketing chain is from Farmers-Traders to Collectors-Wholesalers and Wholesalers to Retailers with a sales volume from farmers of 33,540 kg and a yield presentation of 23.95%. Channel II of the marketing chain from Farmers-Traders to Collectors-Retailers has a farmer sales volume of 44,400 kg and a presentation of 31.71%. Channel III of the marketing chain from Farmers-Wholesalers-Retailers has a sales volume of 45,700 farmers and a presentation of 32.63%. Channel IV of the marketing chain from Farmers-Retailers was 16,380 and the presentation was 11.69%. This shows that the fourth position of the Red Onion marketing chain in Aikmel District in Channels I, II, III, IV experienced an average volume level of 35,005 kg and a presentation of 25 percent. Data for 2023.

The modern economy operates on the principle of division of labor, where each person specializes in producing something, receives wages, and buys needed goods with the money he earns. Therefore, the modern economy is abundant with markets (Ginting, 2011). Manufacturers sell to intermediaries and then sell to retailers. This is how the marketing chain is formed, so this research found several marketing institutions, including:

Marketing Channels I

Type I marketing channel pattern is the longest channel because it involves the four marketing institutions, namely farmers, collectors, wholesalers and retailers. In this pattern, farmers deal directly with collectors, then collectors sell their shallots to wholesalers and wholesalers sell them to retailers and then distribute them to final consumers.

The selling price given by farmers to collectors is IDR 18,875/kg. The amount of shallots marketed is relatively large, ranging from 600 kg to 7,000 kg. A total of 16 farmers chose to sell their shallots to collectors, because they immediately got the proceeds from the sale without having to wait. In line with research by Lekatompessy, Turukay, and Parera (2017) stated that farmers generally sell their products to collectors because they sell more quickly, so farmers can meet their family's needs more quickly. Meanwhile, the costs incurred by farmers are only at the drying stage.

Marketing Channels II

The pattern of marketing channel II is almost the same as the first channel, only this channel does not involve large traders, namely farmers, collectors and retailers and then consumers . In this type of pattern , farmers deal directly with collectors, then collectors sell shallots to retailers and then to consumers .

The selling price given by farmers to collectors is IDR 20,125/kg. The amount of shallots marketed is relatively large, ranging from 900 kg to 10,000 kg. The number of farmers selling shallots on this channel is 16 people. The reason for farmers to sell shallots to collector marketing institutions is that the payments are smooth. After the shallots are at the collector marketing institution, they are then distributed to the next marketing institution, namely the retailer, at a price of IDR 25,000 / kg. The costs incurred by collecting traders are freight, transportation and burlap sack costs. Retailers sell shallots to consumers at a selling price of IDR 31,000/kg.

Marketing Channels III

Channel III pattern is the same as channel II pattern . This channel III pattern involves three channels, namely farmers, wholesalers and retailers. The type of channel formed is that farmers sell their shallots to wholesalers at a price of IDR 19,444/kg. Meanwhile, wholesalers sell shallots to retailers at a price of IDR 22,000/kg. Retailers sell shallots to consumers at prices determined by the retailer in accordance with developments from wholesalers, only the price difference used is Rp. 6,000.

Marketing Channels IV

The channel formed in this type is **Farmer – Retailer** . From the results of searching for this type of marketing channel, researchers found the shortest type of channel compared to other marketing channels . This channel IV pattern is a direct channel where farmers as producers sell directly to retailers without intermediary institutions. In accordance with research by Saragih, Wadu, and Mbana (2022), one of the marketing patterns for shallots is direct marketing from farmers to retailers. In this pattern, farmers market their shallots at a price of 20,071/kg, but the amount sold to retailers is as much as the harvest by farmers, namely 26,000 kg, because the buyers are retailers so the costs incurred in this pattern include sack costs and shallot harvest costs.

Marketing Function

The marketing function is an activity carried out by institutions involved in marketing a product. In other words, this marketing function is carried out by producers and their commodity channel chains, as well as other institutions involved in the marketing process. According to Hanafie (2010), there are three marketing functions, namely the exchange function, physical function and facility provision function, described as follows.

Exchange Function: In this case the product must be sold and purchased at least once during the marketing process. Exchange involves the transfer of ownership of a market system. Participants in these operations are traders (brokers) and agents receiving commissions for connecting buyers and sellers and receiving compensation for services rendered. Pricing is part of the function of the stock market, taking into account the shape of the market and potential competition. This function includes purchasing function activities and sales function activities. Purchasing functions are performed at all levels of the marketing channel. Starting from the procurement of raw materials from primary producers by processors until raw materials are purchased by final consumers from retailers, involving all components of marketing participation. The success of the entire marketing process largely depends on the behavior of the end consumer during purchase. The sales function is an integral part of the exchange function. For manufacturers, the decision to sell is the essence of marketing. Some agricultural products can be sold long term by signing a contract several months before harvest, promising delivery several months later, or storing after harvest and selling several months later.

Physical Function: The physical function in this case is carried out to ensure that buyers get the goods and/or services they want in the right place, at the right time, in the right form and at the right price to increase the usefulness of goods and/or services in marketing. By moving goods and/or services into consumption in the production area, increasing the utility of

time, namely the production of goods and/or services from when they are not needed until when they are needed (from harvest time to shortage) and increasing the utility of the form (*utility of form*), namely the production of goods and/or receipt of services from a more desirable form. Implementation of this function requires the participation of transportation services, post-harvest handling services, and processing services such as cleaning, maintenance, storage, and management.

The variety of types of agricultural products means there are many methods of transporting them to consumers. Some products must be transported quickly immediately after harvest in order to be consumed properly. Transport capacity to meet growing demand must be seriously considered. This problem becomes very important when the transportation network does not yet reach rural areas where the agricultural production process takes place. When adapting transport options are used, attention should also be paid to the geographical conditions of the region. This transportation feature increases the usability of the site for marketable agricultural products.

The post-harvest storage function adds time to the product and is very important for many agricultural products. Given the seasonal nature of agricultural products, recently developed conservation technologies allow fresh fruit and vegetables to be preserved in bacteria-free storage containers for relatively long periods without being frozen. Thus, the processing industry can operate around the clock because raw materials are always available. Primary producers add certain benefits to goods moved through marketing channels. Here, processors play an important role in meeting consumer demand. Processing may involve one or more companies, each company in turn adding a different form of utility.

Function of Providing Facilities: The function of providing facilities is an activity to help the marketing system run more smoothly. This allows buyers, sellers, transporters and processors to carry out their duties without risk and cost and to develop well-organized marketing plans. The function of providing facilities in the marketing process includes several things, including:

- 1) Marketing Information
- 2) Risk Management
- 3) Quality Standardization and Classification

The three marketing functions have been explained above, both the exchange function, physical function, and the function of providing facilities as a result of this research, carried out by the Marketing Institute involved in distributing shallots from farmers to retailers in Aikmel District, described as follows:

1) Farmer Level

Farmers are producers whose role is to produce shallots. The task is to produce shallots ready for distribution. The processes carried out include cultivating the land, preparing seeds, planting, fertilizing, weeding and caring for it wholeheartedly from the vegetative period to the generative period. This process is carried out for 4 harvests in one year.

Before planting shallot bulbs, farmers plow the land using a tractor. Basic fertilization first, after that the farmer makes the bed and then plants, first watering the shallot bulbs. On the second day, farmers sprayed using Full Growth Herbicide. After 5-10 days, new shallot shoots appeared. At the age of 10 days, fertilize and water the 2nd after that until the age of 21 days the farmer does the 3rd fertilization and the 3rd watering. Then after the age of 35 days the farmer does the 4th or final fertilization until watering.

After 50 days the farmer does the final watering and after 60 days the farmer can harvest shallots. Farmers, especially those without partnerships, are starting to look for information on developments in shallot prices. Activities carried out include asking fellow farmers, traders and other information media for young millennial farmers about strategies/processes for marketing their shallot harvest. Farmers harvest shallots by involving family and community members as workers. Depends on the land area and number of plantings. If the number of plants is 900-6000 kg, then it is harvested by a farmer of 5-11 people.

Facility functions such as sorting (separating) are carried out by farmers directly on the land. The sorting process is carried out when the shallots are put into white burlap sacks. This means that before the harvest process, collectors prepare sacks at a price of IDR 4,000 per seed with a capacity of 50 - 60 kg per sack for independent farmers.

In the process of filling shallots into sacks, farmers will separate damaged shallots, especially shallots affected by fruit flies, rotten, broken and others in order to maintain the good quality of shallots. Apart from that, farmers will provide a weight cut, namely 5 kg per 100 kg with the aim of anticipating shrinkage and other damage occurring.

The transportation function carried out by farmers is usually carried out from the harvest field to the roadside (accessible to vehicles/pickups). Meanwhile, if there is no vehicle access, farmers will carry out the transaction process at home, depending on the agreement of both parties.

The promotion and price determination function at the farmer level marketing function is determined depending on several factors, including farmers who will determine the price of shallots if the availability of shallots on the market is very small. Meanwhile market demand is very high. In this position the price of shallots will increase. Where 100% of farmers do not partner, they determine the price of shallots themselves.

The promotional function will be really needed if the price of shallots decreases and the availability of shallots among farmers is quite large, while market demand is very limited. In this position, independent farmers (not partners) will experience losses, because traders rarely look for shallots. In this position, quite a few independent farmers do not harvest.

2) Collecting Traders

The marketing function carried out by collecting traders is in the form of an exchange function, including purchasing and selling functions. The physical function is in the form of a transportation function and the facility function is in the form of market information.

The exchange functions carried out by village collecting traders are the purchasing function and the sales function. In channel I, village collecting traders buy shallots from producers directly using the cash payment method at a price per unit kilo determined by the wholesaler. Next, village collectors sell shallots to wholesalers, where the collectors deliver the shallots to the wholesaler's location using cash payment method.

The physical function carried out by village collecting traders is the transportation function. Where in channel I in this study there were 3 (three) village collector traders selling shallots to wholesalers using means of transportation such as *pick-up trucks*.

The function of the facility carried out by village collecting traders is in the form of market information. Where market information is obtained by village collecting traders, namely regarding the buying price and selling price of shallots obtained from wholesalers.

Collecting traders or wholesalers are traders whose function is to collect farmers' harvests. Then distributed directly to traders and retailers. The role of collectors is very important as a determinant of the continuity of shallots marketed by collectors. Apart from that, wholesalers are very responsible for the quality of shallots that will be accepted by wholesalers and retailers.

If damage occurs due to the farmer's error in the sorting process or there is other damage, it will be the responsibility of the collecting trader, especially since the shallots distributed have been paid in full to the farmer. Because in this position, usually collectors will deduct damage in excess of the 5 kilo filling cut in 100 kg.

Not only that, the collecting traders will play a role in carrying out the transportation function from the farm road (rice field edge) by *picking up*, arranging the goods on *the pick up* then distributing them to all customers. Prior to that, in the process of transporting and arranging goods, traders usually hired mid-day workers at a wage of three people at Rp. 60,000 per person to pick up shallots at the edge of the rice fields and arrange them on pick-ups.

Distribution costs from collectors to wholesale market retailers depend on the delivery destination. If the destination is to go to the main Paok Cut market by pick up then the cost is IDR 300,000 and the Aikmel market costs IDR. 200,000. The location for receiving shallots by collectors is directly at the buyer's location, in this case the main market retailer.

For the payment function, it will be made one to three days after the first delivery up to three times. Then payment is made using a note system, meaning the collector only makes a note upon delivery and will pay after a day to three days later. Meanwhile, payments will be made by transfer via banking services.

3) Wholesalers

The marketing function carried out by wholesalers is the exchange function in the form of buying and selling, the physical function in the form of transportation, packaging, storage and market information. The facility's functions consist of sorting and grading, risk management, and market information. Wholesalers purchase shallots directly from farmers on a per kilo system. Meanwhile, collecting traders come directly to large traders. The payment system is in cash.

The type of transportation used by wholesalers is adjusted to the shipping volume, such as *pick-up trucks* and packaging using sacks. Transportation costs are borne by the wholesaler. The facility function consists of risk management and market information. Shallots can shrink by 3-4% of their initial volume.

Wholesaler marketing institutions are very important in the shallot marketing process in Aikmel District, East Lombok Regency. From the search results, wholesalers are balancing the price of shallots both at the local and national levels. When dealers increase their distribution volume, the marketing of shallots at the local level will increase, commensurate with the increase in the price of shallots in traditional markets. On the other hand, if the distribution volume of shallots decreases, this will be followed by instability in the development of shallots in traditional markets.

This marketing institution receives shallots at home, with a system of delivery by collectors. The method of determining prices by this type of marketing institution depends on price developments in the market, especially seen from the amount of demand. Demand is known from communication media such as *cellphones*. Meanwhile, large traders in the distribution of shallots use fast expeditions.

4) Retailer Marketing Function

This marketing function is very important and determining in the process of distributing shallots to the final consumer, because these retailers are directly in the middle of consumers' lives or trade in the middle of people's lives.

According to Rangkuti (2013), strategy is a comprehensive life plan, describing how the business will achieve all the goals that have been set based on a previously determined mission. Meanwhile, according to Pearce II and Robinson (2008), strategy is a big plan and focuses on the future to interact with competitive situations with the aim of achieving trader or business goals. This is also a concept that needs to be understood and applied by entrepreneurs in all business sectors, including the agricultural sector. Organizational leaders explore the congruence of internal and external forces every day.

This institution obtains red onion price information from direct sellers. They will buy shallots according to their trading needs. This type of institution is very limited in the number of purchases. Average 1 Kg – 5 Kg. Meanwhile, transportation costs will be borne directly by wholesalers or collectors. The sorting function is not carried out by these wholesalers, because they already carry out sorting directly when making purchases at retailers.

5) Analysis of Red Onion Price Determination

Price is one element of the marketing *mix*. Price is one of the most critical elements of a company's marketing strategy. Price is important for marketers, because it is from the price that the company's income and profits are obtained so that the company's survival can be maintained. Price is the only element of the marketing mix that generates revenue, as the other elements only generate costs.

Price is also the most flexible marketing mix element and can change quickly (Hamid, et al. 2023). Price is the amount of money and/or something else along with the benefits needed to get a product (Etzel, Walker, and Stanton, 1997, p. 274). In other words, the price is what we pay to get something. The price setting process carried out by traders includes several stages.

The stages of pricing are (1) determining the pricing objectives; (2) estimate demand for the good and its price elasticity; (3) anticipating reactions in competition; (4) determine the expected market share; (5) choosing a pricing strategy to reach the target market; (6) consider the company's marketing policy; (7) choosing a price calculation method, setting price levels, and adjusting the price structure to variations in demand and costs in each segment (Ariasih, et al. 2023).

To complete the marketing function analysis, marketing price standards are needed. The determinants of marketing prices for shallots in Aikmel District in 2023, including marketing cycles I, II, III, IV, are explained in detail as follows.

In marketing cycle I, farmers get information from collectors. Then there is bargaining, then the collectors determine the price. Collectors sell their shallots to wholesalers by selling the shallots according to market prices. Likewise, wholesalers sell their shallots to retailers.

In marketing cycle II, where farmers ask the price of shallots from collectors directly and bargain with the farmers. Then it is determined by the collectors and the collectors sell the shallots to retailers according to market prices.

In marketing cycle III, farmers sell their shallots to wholesalers and get information directly from the market and wholesalers. Then the wholesaler sells the shallots to wholesalers at prices according to market prices.

In marketing cycle IV, farmers get information on shallot prices from fellow farmers and social media. Then the farmer asks the retailer for the price and bargaining occurs. Then the retailer determines the price.

It can be concluded that the price sold by farmers to collectors is based on price requests from buyers, both wholesalers and collectors at the sub-district level. The price determination process in this model occurs when the availability of shallots on the market still looks normal. This is different from the condition where red onions are starting to decrease. Usually in this condition farmers have a bigger role in determining the price of shallots. The bargaining value of farmers when shallots are scarce will determine the price of shallots received by traders. However, most of the onion prices are determined by traders.

Marketing Efficiency: Marketing efficiency in this research in analysis through operational efficiency and price efficiency. The size indicators in determining operational efficiency are commonly used in several previous studies, namely the size of the marketing margin, the farmer's share, as well as the costs and benefits of the marketing Technical Index (IET) efficiency or often referred to as the profit to cost ratio.

Marketing Margin: In the process of analyzing marketing margin data, researchers found four types of marketing channels. The marketing channels that are the focus of discussion in this research are channels I, II, III and IV. Based on the results of marketing margin data analysis, marketing channel I is the longest channel. The total marketing margin in channel I is IDR 11,125 with total marketing costs of IDR 1,795, and the total profit in this marketing channel is IDR 9,330. The high marketing margin is caused by the length of the marketing channel. This is because this marketing channel involves four market players, namely farmers, collectors, wholesalers and retailers.

The length and shortness of the marketing channel really determines prices, margins and profits. The longer the marketing channel, the higher the marketing margin. The higher the price the retailer will accept. In this case the marketing channel is said to be inefficient. The highest cost of marketing red onions is in channel II, namely Rp. 2,000 and the highest profit in marketing shallots is in channel I, namely Rp. 9,000. because in this channel farmers directly sell their shallot production to retailers.

Table 12. Shallot Marketing Margin in Aikmel District 2023.

Marketing channel	I	II	III	IV
Farmer				
Selling price	18,875	20,125	19,444	20,071
Sales Costs				
Profit				
P.P				
Purchase price	18,875	20,125		
Cost	395	1000		
Selling price	20,500	25,000		
Margin	1,625	4,875		
Profit	1,230	3,875		
PB				
Purchase price	20,500		19,444	
Cost	400		500	
Selling price	23,000		22,000	
Margin	2,500		2,556	
Profit	2,100		2,056	
P.R				
Purchase price	23,000	25,000	22,000	20,071
Cost	1,000	1,000	1,000	1,000
Selling price	30,000	31,000	28,000	26,000
Margin	7,000	6,000	6,000	5,929
Profit	6,000	5,000	5,000	4,929
Total cost	1,795	1,322	1,500	1,000
Total Margin	11,125	10,875	8,556	5,929
Total Profit	9,330	9,553	7,056	4,929

Farmers' Share: Based on the data presented in Limbong and Sitorus (1987) in Syaifullah (2014), Farmer's Share is an analytical tool used as a comparison between the price paid by consumers and the price received by farmers. Farmer's Share is inversely proportional to marketing margin. The higher the marketing margin, the lower the Farmer's Share received by farmers. Farmer's share analysis is used to determine the share of the price received by farmers from the price received by final consumers. The higher the producer share, the better the market performance from the producer (farmer) side. Rahim and Astuti, (2007).

Farmer's share is the share obtained by farmers from the price paid by final consumers (Suminartika and Iin, 2017). Another opinion expressed by Riyadh (2018) states that farmer's share is a marketing analysis comparing the price received by farmers with the price paid by final consumers. According to Iswahyudi and Sustiyana (2019) farmer's share is an indicator showing operational efficiency in the portion received by farmers from a marketing activity. The size of the farmer's share is greatly influenced by the marketing channels used and the selling price at the retail level. The size of the share received by farmers shows whether the distribution of results between collecting traders, wholesalers and retailers is equal to farmers (Arbi et al, 2018). The more marketing intermediaries there are, the smaller the share received by farmers.

The results of Farmer's Share data analysis in research on shallot marketing in East Lombok Regency are shown in Table.

Table 13. Farmer's Share on Shallot Marketing Channels in Aikmel District 2023.

No	Marketing channel	Farmer Level Price IDR/Kg	Consumer Level Price IDR/Kg	Farmer's Share (%)
1	Channel I	18,875	30,000	62.92
2	Channel II	20,125	31,000	64.92
3	Channel III	19,444	28,000	69.44
4	IV line	20,071	26,000	77.20

Source: Processed Primary Data (2023)

From the results of data analysis carried out in the table above, it shows that the largest Farmer's Share received by farmers in the shallot marketing channel in Aikmel District is in marketing channel IV, namely 77.20%, because the marketing channel in this type of marketing is very short. Meanwhile, in the first marketing channel, Farmer's Share received by farmers was 64.92%. The length and shortness of the marketing channel affects the level of share received by farmers.

Profit to Cost Ratio: According to Tinur, Alamsyah & Naenggolan (2015), the profit over cost ratio is one method used to see the distribution of profits and costs incurred by marketing institutions. If the π/C value is more than one ($\pi/C > 1$) then the marketing activity is profitable, conversely if the π/C value is less than one ($\pi/C < 1$) then the activity does not provide a profit. The Profit and Marketing Cost Ratio is the percentage of profit to marketing costs at each marketing institution used to determine the spread of margins. Using the π_i/c_i formula. Where: π_i : profits received by the i-th institution c_i : costs incurred by the i-th institution. If the ratio value is > 1 then marketing is said to be efficient, whereas if the ratio value is < 1 , marketing is said to be inefficient (Asmarantaka, 2014).

Based on the marketing margin value obtained, it can be seen the level of profit ratio to costs incurred by the marketing institution. This ratio shows the amount of profit obtained against the marketing costs incurred by each marketing institution. The higher the ratio value, the greater the profit obtained (Limbong and Sitorus 1987).

The results of data analysis on the profit-to-cost ratio in this research are as shown in the table.

Table 14. Shallot Marketing Profit Ratio in Each Channel Marketing is seen from the Total Marketing Costs in 2023.

No	Marketing channel	Total Marketing Costs (Rp/kg)	Total (Rp/kg)	Profit	Profit Ratio/ Cost (%)
1	Channel I	1,795	9,330	5,197	
2	Channel II	2,000	8,875	4,437	
3	Channel III	1,500	7,056	4,704	
4	IV line	1,000	4,929	4,929	

Source: Processed Primary Data (2023)

In the table above, the results of the profit versus cost data analysis above show that the marketing channels for shallots in Aikmel District from channel I to channel III are 0.167-0.286%, because the total marketing costs in all marketing channels are smaller than the total selling price in all marketing channel. The first marketing channel shows that the total value of the ratio of profits to marketing costs is 0.400%, meaning it is greater than 1. This result is obtained after **the Total Profit (π i) is divided by the Total Marketing Cost (Ci) / Total Profit (π i) Lowest Price Share At the Highest Price**. However, this type of marketing channel is very long, involving all existing marketing institutions. Meanwhile, the lowest profit was in marketing channel I, namely 0.167. Meanwhile in channels II and III the value of the profit to cost ratio is greater, 3.75, which is more than the profit. However, in this marketing channel the researchers only reached Aikmel and Paok Motong retailers.

Marketing Efficiency: In this research, marketing efficiency is seen from the results of calculating marketing margin, farmer's share, profit to cost ratio using the technical efficiency index approach. Technical Efficiency Index (IET) Calkins and Wang show that the most efficient channel is channel 4 of the four channels there is a value of 0.41. Channel 1 is more efficient than channels 2 and 3, and channel 3 is more efficient than channel 2. This is usually because the profits obtained from marketing channel 2 are greater than the smallest total marketing costs. The comparison between profits and marketing costs can be seen in the following table.

Table 15. Economic Efficiency Index for Each Channel

Information	Channel I	Channel II	Channel III	IV line
Cost (Rp/Kg)	1,869	1,322	1500	1,000
Sales Volume	33,540	44,400	45,700	16,380
Distance (Km)	15	15	15	15
IET	0.37	0.20	0.22	0.41

Source: *Processed Primary Data (2023)*

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion: Based on the results of data analysis and discussions described in the previous chapters, several things can be concluded as follows:

1) Market behavior seen from the shallot marketing channels in Aikmel District forms four types of marketing channels involving five marketing institutions, namely:

- a. Farmers - Collectors - Wholesalers - Retailers with a sales volume of 33,540 kg.
- b. Farmers – Collectors – Retailers with a sales volume of 44,400 kg.
- c. Farmers – Wholesalers – Retailers with a sales volume of 45,700 kg.
- d. Farmers – Retailers with a sales volume of 16,380 kg

2) The marketing function of shallots can be summarized through several main aspects, namely:

- a. Farmer

Farmers carry out sales marketing functions, marketing costs and risk coverage costs, market information.

- b. Collector

Collectors carry out the functions of marketing, purchasing, selling, transportation, storage, sorting/standardization, marketing costs, risk bearing, market information.

- c. Wholesalers

Wholesalers carry out marketing functions, purchasing, selling, transportation, storage, sorting/standardization, marketing costs, risk bearing, market information.

d. Retailer

Retailers carry out marketing, purchasing, sales, risk, market information functions.

3) The shallot market in Aikmel District is classified as efficient when viewed from the indicators of marketing margin, farmer share and profit to cost ratio.

4) The most efficient marketing channel for shallots in East Lombok Regency is channel IV (from farmers directly to retailers).

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